

BuildingSmart Use-Case Definition – Generative Design Modeler

Section 1: MetaData

1.1 Identification of the document- This format section allows the provision of the title of the Use-case along with a short text describing it and author details.

Title:

EU ASHVIN- Template

GENERATIVE DESIGN MODELER USE CASE

ASHVIN: Assistants for Healthy, Safe and Productive Virtual Construction Design, Operation & Maintenance using a Digital Twin.

Short Text:

Parametric design to optimize productivity, resource efficiency, and safety during early stages

Project Status:

Finished

Publisher:

N/A

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Introduction:

This document provides background and describes a use case of applying historic data from past construction operations that were tracked with construction site digital twin technology to support future design activities. The use can propose to use historic data, identify performance metrics and then use parametric modeling, generative design, optimization, and pareto-front-based decision-making to support help designers already in early design stages.

1.2 Imprint:

Project Group:

N/A

Partners:

Joan Evelyn Ongodia (Technische Universität Berlin), Timo Hartmann (Technische Universität Berlin)

Handling (can be edited based on preference):

N/A

Section 2: Use-Case Definition

2.1 Data Sheets & Standards

N/A

2.2 General Definition of the Use-Case

USE CASE DESCRIPTION	
Title	Generative Design Modeler Use Case
Goal	Optimize productivity, resource efficiency, and safety of construction work during early design stages
Description	To create a parametric design, which is a design method in which features, such as building elements and engineering components, are shaped based on algorithmic processes rather than direct manipulation, to optimize productivity, resource efficiency, and safety by using historic data from past construction operations that were tracked with construction site digital twin technology to support future design activities .
Input Data	Design Inputs which are geometric parameters such as length and width of the construction element and functions from historic data from past construction operations
Sequence of actions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identification of project specifications and requirements 2. Parameters from historic evidence of similar past projects 3. Development of a parametric model design 4. Generative design of various optimization alternatives
Primary actors	Architects, Civil Engineers, Civil Engineering Companies
Secondary actors	Designers
Pre-conditions	Adequate amount of evidence based design data of the site
Trigger	Development of parametric model
Post-conditions	
Frequency of use	Every design
Support planned for	ASHVIN
UC Created by	
Date of last update	

Figure 1 Use Case Description

Aim and Scope:

The proposed use case aims to present the end-user with optimal design option scenarios which have resource efficiency, less carbon emission and less cost, based on the evidenced historic data from past construction projects to find the more suitable conceptual architectural designs. The developed parametric model is used for the generative design explorations. The design alternatives are evaluated and evolved iteratively by adjusting inputs of the parametric model to achieve a set of optimal design alternatives.

Objectives:

This document provides for using the parametric model as input, the generative design process generates various designs which are analyzed, ranked, evolved, explored, and integrated. The outcome of the generative design process is a set of optimal design options. This generative design approach increases productivity in design because various design solutions are computationally generated, implying that fewer time/work hours are required. In addition, the iterative process allows design modifications to be done quickly. To perform the generative design process, the input parametric model undergoes an optimization study.

The optimization study computationally explores design alternatives based on the project goals, variable parameters, and constraints. The goals are the performance indicators (PIs) based on the desirable high-performance criteria. The variables give a range of parametric values which the model can adopt during the optimization as the algorithms investigate (evaluate and evolve) trade-offs between the Performance Indicators. Constraints dictate the limits/boundary extents so that future evolutions of the design solutions are restricted to fit within the limits. The results of the optimization study are the various design alternatives.

The Performance Indicators considered under the productivity Key Performance Indicator are the work hours for the construction time. Construction Safety Performance Indicators include weight-lifting capacities, incident rates, and accident costs. The safety Performance Indicators consider the cranes which are the main source of construction incidents and accidents.

2.3 Overall Process:

This Generative Design Modeler use case mostly interacts with the historical data and key performance indicators such as productivity, safety and resource efficiency.

The overall process map for the use case is presented in Figure 2. Evidence-based data knowledge base should be used at the start of this process. After that, parameters from evidence-based data should be compared with the project requirements. A parametric model design for the new project should be developed. The design alternatives are evaluated and evolved iteratively by adjusting inputs of the parametric model to achieve a set of optimal design alternatives. In the end, if one model is ok, there is no need to use generative design. If it is not ok and more alternatives are needed, generative design steps should be processed.

1. Generate,
2. Analyze,
3. Rank,
4. Evolve,
5. Explore
6. Integrate.

During the ranking, Key Performance Indicator scores are used. In the end, the most optimal final design could be created.

Figure 2 Process Map

Implementation on #8 Footbridge in Germany

The City of Dortmund is planning to replace the existing Lindemannstrasse foot and cycle path bridge, which connects Max-Ophüls-Platz with the forecourt of the Dortmund Trade Fair Centre. The bridge crosses the Rheinlanddamm, a highly frequented inner-city main road with six lanes. 51°29'52.1"N 7°27'11.7"E are the coordinates of the footbridge location.

The project background provided by the client includes a bridge design that envisages the superstructure, stairs and supports as a monolithic, jointless steel construction. The continuous superstructure has a total length of approximately 210m and is regularly supported at intervals of approx. 50-60m by splayed V-shaped supports. The span of the superstructure is approx. 35-48m in free length and approx. 14-17m in the support area. The cantilever of the loops from the column axis to the abutment is approx. 17.5m from the support axis to the abutment. The new barrier-free 210m long bridge will replace an old existing foot and cycle path bridge crossing over a busy highway road. The proposed bridge is a girder suspension bridge with pile-pier foundations. The project requires i) safe and cost-efficient construction, ii) sustainable and resource-efficient construction, and iii) increases in design for productivity. However, project-specific challenges include i) protecting the existing tree species, and ii) being crowded underground with various utilities including gas, water, and electricity.

Project partner SBP helps the demonstration of the evidence based and generative design methods using their large portfolio of footbridges. Evidence based historical data create the project database. It contains data, experience and knowledge from previously implemented footbridges. The data will be filtered according to project-relevant performance and key performance indicators, i.e. safety, productivity, costs and resource efficiency, and the output of this filtering serve as an orientation aid, as a benchmark, in the ongoing design process. Designers can understand which parameters should be used in the project. This database serves to assess design variants on an ongoing basis in the design phase.

Figure 3 Google™ path showing bridge axis, and our built parametric model on the right

With the length fixed as 210m for bridge crossing, suitable geometric parameters for the width and thickness are adopted as design inputs from the historic evidence knowledge base (see Figure 6). For example, the parametric model of the footbridge was created in Dynamo™ using 210m, 1.8m, and 0.1m for the bridge length, width, and thickness, respectively. In the next step, alternative design options of the parametric model were created.

#	Mathematical functions embedded as fitness functions in Dynamo™ custom nodes
1	$\text{Carbon footprint [kgCO}_2\text{e]} = 4128.9 \text{ kgCO}_2\text{e} - 442.3 \frac{\text{kgCO}_2\text{e}}{\text{m}} \cdot L - 5333.9 \frac{\text{kgCO}_2\text{e}}{\text{m}} \cdot W + 38107.0 \frac{\text{kgCO}_2\text{e}}{\text{m}} \cdot T + 189.9 \frac{\text{kgCO}_2\text{e}}{\text{m}^2} \cdot L \cdot W - 219.2 \frac{\text{kgCO}_2\text{e}}{\text{m}^2} \cdot L \cdot T$
2	$\text{Cost [€]} = -249792 \text{ €} + 13318 \frac{\text{€}}{\text{m}} \cdot L - 109904 \frac{\text{€}}{\text{m}} \cdot W + 2172682 \frac{\text{€}}{\text{m}} \cdot T$
3	$\text{Construction time [days]} = 84.92 \text{ days} - 4.4 \frac{\text{days}}{\text{m}} \cdot L + 10.65 \frac{\text{days}}{\text{m}} \cdot W - 2.16 \frac{\text{days}}{\text{m}} \cdot T + 1.99 \frac{\text{days}}{\text{m}^2} \cdot L \cdot W + 7.99 \frac{\text{days}}{\text{m}^2} \cdot L \cdot T + 23.76 \frac{\text{days}}{\text{m}^2} \cdot W \cdot T - 2.59 \frac{\text{days}}{\text{m}^3} \cdot L \cdot W \cdot T$
4	$\text{Weight [T]} = \frac{L \cdot W \cdot T \cdot \text{unit weight} \frac{\text{Kg}}{\text{m}^3}}{1000}$

Figure 4 Mathematical functions derived from parameter-relationships in the historic evidence

Changeable design variables	Lower limit (LL)	Upper limit (UL)
length of deck segments (m)	23-50	50.5-760
width of deck segments (m)	1.8-3	3.5-11.5
thickness of deck segments (m)	0.1-0.5	0.55-1.2
deck_area (m ²)	61.6	10580
time_per_area (days/m ²)	0.11	5.40
cost_per_area (€/m ²)	1750	22727
carbon_per_area (KgCo ₂ e/m ²)	9.31	42.83

Figure 5 Changing design variables with their limits

To create the alternative design options, the mathematical functions from the historic evidence knowledge base were solved using both the parameter ranges (minimum – maximum) and KPI-values/area, as variable parameters. On the other hand, (i) the fixed bridge crossing length of 210m provides the constraint, while (ii) the client-specified traffic load of 500Kg/m² and the 7850Kg/m³ unit weight of steel were the generative design constants. The design options are then recommended as a set of pareto-optimal design solutions for the footbridge (see Figure 7).

Figure 7 shows examples of computations for the resource-efficiency KPI-values for each of the three recommended design options for the demo8 footbridge. Performance Indicator-based models that can be obtained are summarized in Figure 6.

Examples of PI-based models are summarized in Figure 6. The PIs considered under the productivity KPI are the workhours for the construction time. Construction safety PIs include weight-lift capacities, incident rates and accident costs. Resource-efficiency PIs comprise of carbon and CO₂ emissions. The CO₂ emissions PI is justified by the equipment operations as the main sources of gaseous emissions. Cost PIs can include direct costs and life-cycle costs which are related to the construction project.

KPI models	Descriptions of the performance indicators (PIs)
Productivity model	<p>Workhours: (Optimising the overall time required for construction)</p>
Safety model	<p>Weight-lift capacities: (Explore component weights for planning adequate equipment capacities to minimize incident rates and accident costs)</p> <p>Incident rates: (Optimising crane operator’s line of sight for safe operations)</p>
Resource-efficiency model	<p>Carbon: (Explore carbon footprint to minimize environmental impacts)</p> <p>Greenhouse gas (GHG) CO₂ emissions: (Optimising equipment positions and reach lengths to minimize GHG CO₂ emissions)</p>

Figure 6 Parametric models which validate design using evidenced historic data

Figure 7 Set of pareto-optimal designs based on carbon, cost and time KPIs

Deck segment length (m)	Deck segment width (m)	Deck segment thickness (m)	Carbon (KgCO ₂ e)	Cost (€)	Time (days)	Weight (T)
35.857	3.076	0.776	16283.358	1414059.32	236	671.950
33.012	5.097	1.128	29127.103	981158.02	269	1490.383
105.016	10.500	0.123	112904.011	502037.57	1712	1061.000

Figure 8 Geometries of the recommended pareto-optimal designs

Changing variable parameter (unit)	Values (minimum – maximum ranges)	Treatment as design input
Length (m)	23 - 760	Applied ranges of (23 - 50) and (50.05 - 760) as lower and upper limits, respectively for the generative design optimization process. However, in this study this parameter is constrained to 210m, corresponding with the project-specific requirements for bridge crossing.
deck_width (m)	1.8 - 11.5	Applied ranges of (1.8 - 3) and (3.05 - 11.5) as lower and upper limits, respectively for the generative design optimization process.

Changing variable parameter (unit)	Values (minimum – maximum ranges)	Treatment as design input
deck_thickness (m)	0.1 - 1.2	Applied ranges of (0.1 - 0.5) and (0.55 - 1.2) as lower and upper limits, respectively for the generative design optimization process.
deck_area (m ²)	61.6 - 10580	Not considered. Instead, actual area is computed based on generated geometry
Construction time (days)	81 - 1310	Applied ranges of (81 - 500) and (500.05 - 1310) as lower and upper limits respectively, for the generative design optimization process.
Construction time per_area (days/m ²)	0.1 - 5.4	Applied ranges of (0.1- 3) and (3.05 – 5.4) as lower and upper limits respectively, for the generative design optimization process.
Construction cost per_area (€/m ²)	1750 - 22727.3	Applied ranges of (1750 - 10000) and (10000.05 – 22727.3) as lower and upper limits respectively, for the generative design optimization process.
Construction carbon footprint per_area (kgCO ₂ e/m ²)	9.3 - 42.8	Applied ranges of (9.3 - 25) and (25.05 – 42.8) as lower and upper limits respectively, for the generative design optimization process.

Figure 9 Recommended set of pareto-optimal design solutions

Figure 10 Resource-efficiency KPI-values for the footbridge design alternatives

Implementation on #11 Footbridge in Germany

The 350 m long S-curve Weinbergbridge (**Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**11) for pedestrian crossing the Havel river in Rathenow, Germany is supported by slightly angled (25°) steel arches over the river. Its unique hangers are located on radial cantilevers that almost reach the arch planes to significantly reduce the bending stresses within the arch. Its arches uniquely terminate at the 10 m height of the superstructure thereby short circuiting the horizontal thrust via a tie cable. Thirdly, the 1110 m² bridge deck uniquely widens to allow for seating space on its torsional rigid steel hollow box section. The geometrical embodiments of the parametric model, based on the imported input (Figure 12).

Figure 11 S-curve Weinbergbridge pedestrian bridge across the Havel river in Rathenow, Germany - Overview

Changing variable parameter (unit)	Values (minimum – maximum ranges)	Treatment as design input
Length (m)	28 - 350	Applied ranges of (28 - 100) and (100.05 - 350) as lower and upper limits, respectively for the generative design optimization process. However, in this case study this parameter is constrained to 350m, corresponding with the project-specific requirements for bridge crossing.
Deck_width (m)	2.5 - 8	Applied ranges of (2.5 - 4) and (4.05 - 8) as lower and upper limits, respectively for the generative design optimization process.
Deck_thickness (m)	0.2 – 0.68	Applied ranges of (0.2 - 0.4) and (0.45 – 0.68) as lower and upper limits, respectively for the generative design optimization process.

Figure 12 Parametric extents from the evidence-based design assistant DT knowledgebase

In addition to the changing variables, the design constants and constraints were adopted based on project-specific requirements (see Figure 13). Using the imported data, the 3D parametric model of the bridge was built in the Dynamo™ by locking the actual length to 350m. Other foot-bridge features included the width (W) and thickness (T) of the footbridge deck that were varied in between the ranges extracted from the knowledgebase data. Additionally, deck the segment length (L) was included in the study to analyze the impact of various segmentation strategies for planning the construction phase.

Constant and Constraint Parameters	Value	Reference source
Constants (unchanging parameters)		
Material unit weight (kg/m ³)	7850	Based on steel material, as specified
Constraints (fixed parameters)		
Total bridge length (m)	350	Site constraint, as requirement for crossing the Havel river from the Weinberg-Park to the Optikpark in Rathenow, Germany

Figure 13 Constant and constraint parameters from project-specific requirements

Various design alternatives can be generated using the parametric model developed in the previous section. The various alternatives support early-stage decision making because each design alternative will be evaluated based on their performance according to a set of KPI-values. To create the various alternatives, mathematical functions (Figure 14) from knowledgebase were coded in the Dynamo environment as custom nodes for computing performance indicator values (PI-values). This study specifically addresses four KPIs of construction resource-efficiency – carbon footprint, construction cost, productivity – construction time, and construction safety – liftable weights.

Equation #1 computes carbon footprint as a function of the deck segment length, deck width, deck thickness, deck segment area, and construction carbon footprint per_area. It calculates the corresponding carbon footprint for each generated design alternative. Different solution options are explored to give all possible design solutions. The deck area changes according to the different multiples of deck segment lengths and deck widths. The objective for the optimization fitness function is to minimize the carbon footprint. Then, the computed values obtained are the optimization results of the various design alternatives and it is part of considering the resource-efficiency KPI.

Equation #2 computes cost as a function of the deck segment length, deck width, deck thickness, deck segment area, deck segment volume and the construction cost per area. It calculates the corresponding carbon footprint for each generated design alternative. Different design solution options are explored and their corresponding construction cost is calculated. The objective for the optimization fitness function is to minimize the construction cost. The computed cost values obtained are the optimization results of the various design alternatives and it is part of the cost KPI. Equation #3 computes time as a function of the deck segment length, deck width, deck thickness, deck segment area, deck segment volume, and the construction time per_area. Different design solutions options are explored based on the variable parameter ranges and their corresponding construction time is calculated. The objective set for this variable for the optimization fitness function is to minimize the construction time. Then, the computed values obtained are the optimization results based on the automatic exploration of the various design alternatives. Construction time is part of the productivity KPI.

In a similar way, equation #4 helps compute weights of deck segments as a product of the deck segment length, deck width, deck thickness, and the unit weight, and material weight unit. Different design options are explored and the corresponding weight for the segments is calculated. The objective set for this variable for the optimization fitness function is to minimize the weight of the deck segments. Then, the computed values obtained are the optimization results based on the automatic exploration of various design alternatives. Weight of the deck segments linked to the safety KPI, in regards that the weights of deck segments for planning adequate equipment lift capacities. Construction safety planning considers adequate equipment lift capacities which correspond with the weights of physical components to be lifted and installed during construction.

#	Mathematical functions embedded as fitness functions in Dynamo™ custom nodes
1	$Cost[€] = -354903.5€ + 7091.4 \frac{€}{m} \cdot Length - 343958.8 \frac{€}{m} \cdot Width + 6749652.6 \frac{€}{m} \cdot Thickness$
2	$Carbonfootprint[kgCO_2e] = 5049400kgCO_2e + 91500 \frac{kgCO_2e}{m} \cdot Length$
3	$Constructiontime[days] = 360.5days + 1.3 \frac{days}{m} \cdot Length$
4	$Weight[T] = \frac{L \cdot W \cdot T \cdot unitweight \frac{Kg}{m^3}}{1000}$

Figure 14 Mathematical functions for Arch bridges from the footbridge knowledgebase

The optimization problem is set as a multi objective optimization, with the purpose of minimizing the objectives set for each output parameter and fulfil the constraints. To automatically iterate over various design alternatives (with the scope of generate, analyse, asses each one of them) an optimization algorithm is employed. In our case we chose genetic algorithm.

Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable. 5 shows the set of pareto-optimal design solutions which are recommended for construction as they provide a good trade-off between the set of objectives. The pareto-optimal designs are those non-dominated solutions. Figure 15 gives the geometries and KPI-values for some of the recommended designs based on the results of KPI-values. The pareto-optimal design options have been arranged based on the shortest duration, assuming a time-sensitive contract.

Figure 15 Set of recommended pareto-optimal designs based on carbon, cost and time KPIs

Deck segment length (m)	Deck segment width (m)	Deck segment thickness (m)	Carbon (KgCO ₂ eq)	Cost (€)	Time (days)	Weight (T)
66.2392638	2.614	0.307	11110292.645	1284592.06	447	416.693
87.861	2.776	0.603	5057439.279	3385611.87	475	1155.281
114.444	4.001	0.226	15520994.869	607844.94	510	813.515

Figure 16 Geometries of the recommended pareto-optimal designs

Examples of PI-based models are summarized in Figure 6 in the first implementation example. The PIs considered under the productivity KPI are the workhours for the construction time. Construction safety PIs include weight-lift capacities, incident rates and accident costs. Resource-efficiency PIs comprise of carbon and CO₂ emissions. The CO₂ emissions PI is justified by the equipment operations as the main sources of gaseous emissions. Cost PIs can include direct costs and life-cycle costs which are related to the construction project

The computationally generated designs be sorted to eliminate erroneous solutions as the ones shown in Figure 17.

The mathematical functions historic footbridge knowledgebase are experimental, yet it serves as proof of concept for the proposed data-driven approach. Functions which comprise of majority geometric features are better to use than those which consider only a few features. This implies

that designers can independently assess the functions and adopt the most suitable option. This enables transparency in design and enables designers to understand the basis of developed design solutions.

Deck segment length (m)	Deck segment width (m)	Deck segment thickness (m)	Carbon (KgCO ₂ e)	Cost (€)	Time (days)	Weight (T)
122.489	6.454	0.239	16257098.31	-93744.06	520	1482.527
88.623	4.9	0.202	13158360.21	-50553.43	476	687.532
122.489	6.515	0.239	16257098.31	-114724.37	520	1496.538

Figure 17 Examples of erroneous solutions

In summary, productivity and safety in early-stage design are improved when the historic data from past projects is used. This is because the new early-stage design will be based on favourable values of the geometric parameters which ensure higher construction performance. This study demonstrates the application of insights from the historic data (geometric extents and mathematical functions) evidence-based design assistant. The geometric extents are used to develop the parametric model. This aspect supports safety in design since the developed model excludes mistakes of previous past projects. When various design alternatives are required, the mathematical functions are used in the optimization study to generate various design alternatives. This aspect improves productivity in design because many designs are generated at once.

2.4 Disciplines:

Investigation discipline- risk assessment;

Project Management discipline- cost estimation, proposal preparation, and scheduling

2.5 Life Cycle Stages:

Production information and construction.

Section 3: Process-definition

Life cycle stages: Construction stage

Production information and construction

Section 4: Exchange Requirements

In Figure 18, exchange requirements among steps are shown. Firstly, with the preparation of a geometric parameters and mathematical functions from evidence based database. After this, a parametric design model is created by parametric modeling software. With this parametric design, generative design is applied to create final designs. In the end, these final designs can be sent to a visualization software.

Figure 18 Exchange Requirements

Section 5: Change Log

This is a section only for changes made after publishing to the front end